

AI-Driven Knowledge Graphs for Future Foods:

Optimizing Sustainable Protein Alternatives and Reducing Environmental Impact

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Abstract:

This study introduces an AI-powered knowledge graph (KG) framework to support sustainable food systems by optimizing protein alternatives and analyzing their environmental impact. Unlike traditional life cycle assessments, KGs provide real-time, structured, and queryable insights into sustainability indicators such as carbon footprint, water use, and land use. The research shows that substituting 20% of animal proteins with plant-based alternatives like legumes or microalgae could cut emissions by ...

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Keywords:

Knowledge graphs, AI, sustainable proteins, alternative proteins, future foods, bio-manufacturing, precision nutrition, environmental sustainability, UN SDGs.

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